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ACTIVITIES OF PUBLIC ORGANIZATIONS OF UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: The article examines the key stages of the formation and development of these organizations, their role in the formation of civil society, as well as emerging problems and challenges. Particular attention is paid to successful practices and achievements, as well as modern trends and innovations in their activities.

Keywords: Public organizations, civil society, reforms, social changes, political parties, trade unions, youth organizations, creative associations, electronic platforms.

Introduction. Public associations are associations of citizens registered in accordance with the law. Public associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan include trade unions, political parties, societies of scientists and youth organizations, creative associations, mass movements and other associations of citizens. Public associations are a manifestation of popular initiative, active participation in public life, an integral part of democracy and the rule of law, a way of life typical of a civil society. Public associations are created for the purposes of: realizing and protecting the rights and freedoms of people in the civil, economic, social and cultural spheres, strengthening their participation in the management of state and public affairs, satisfying their professional and amateur interests, developing scientific, technical and artistic creativity, protecting public health, participating in charitable activities, conducting activities in the field of profession, culture, health care, physical education and sports, protecting nature, historical and cultural monuments, educating citizens in the spirit of patriotism and humanity, expanding international relations and activities in other areas not prohibited by law.

Methods and methodology of research. In the study of public organizations in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, the following methods were employed to analyze their activities, challenges, and developments: historical analysis, archival research, chronological review, legal and policy analysis, comparative analysis, quantitative analysis, statistical data analysis.

These methods collectively provide a comprehensive understanding of the activities, challenges, and development of public organizations in Uzbekistan, facilitating a nuanced analysis of their role and impact in the context of independence and beyond.

Results. Laws and regulations on public associations are defined in Chapter XIII of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law "On Public Associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (February 15, 1991). [1] They state that the state ensures the observance of the rights and legitimate interests of public associations, creates equal legal opportunities for everyone to participate in public associations. State bodies and officials have no right to interfere in the activities of public associations, and public associations have no right to interfere in the activities of state bodies and officials.

In recent years, our country has been implementing consistent reforms to support non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions, create conditions for them, guarantee their freedom of activity, strengthen social partnership between state bodies and them, and improve the legal framework regulating this area. [2]

As a result, over the past four years, the number of non-governmental non-profit organizations, which are the main institutions of civil society, has increased by 20.7 percent, and 187 large republican non-governmental non-profit organizations have begun their activities. activity.

Today, there are more than nine thousand non-governmental non-profit organizations operating in our country, which play an important role in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities, democratic values, and achieving social, cultural and educational goals.

As a result of the measures taken to create comfort and convenience for the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, the regulatory framework was further improved to meet modern democratic requirements and international standards. As a result, about 20 laws, documents of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and government resolutions were adopted. [1,3]

In particular, in order to further ensure the freedom of activity of non-governmental non-profit organizations, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 4, 2018 PF-5430 "On measures to radically increase the role of civil society" institutions in the process of democratic renewal of the country." This Decree created a number of conveniences for non-governmental non-profit organizations in the implementation of their activities, on the basis of the Decree, conditions were created for coordinating with the justice authorities the events planned for implementation by non-governmental non-profit organizations. - commercial organizations from June 1, 2018 were cancelled and a notification procedure was introduced. As a result, as a result of the elimination of one of the bureaucratic obstacles in the activities of NGOs, the number of events held by NGOs increased over the year to 10,665. [4]

As well as funds and property received from foreign states, international and foreign organizations, citizens of foreign states or other persons on their behalf for the implementation of the tasks stipulated by their charters (regulations), to the accounts of non-governmental non-profit organizations. , their receipt is determined by the registering authority, after proper approval, it is decided to use them without any obstacles.

In addition, since December 1, 2019, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan launched the portal www.e-ngo.uz, which provides the opportunity to provide a number of services related to its activities in electronic form, in order to facilitate unauthorized access to information. - state non-profit organizations. [6]

In electronic form through this portal:

- state registration and re-registration of non-governmental non-profit organizations and their symbols;
- informing about planned events of non-governmental non-profit organizations;
- submission of annual reports on the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations;
- consent to receive funds and property from foreign states, international and foreign organizations, citizens of foreign states or other persons on their behalf by non-governmental non-profit organizations;
- electronic submission of documents for accreditation of employees of non-governmental non-profit organizations who are foreign citizens, as well as their family members who are dependent on them.

As a result of the reforms carried out, "Houses of Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations" were created in the center of the regions, problems related to the construction of about 500 non-governmental non-profit organizations, their socially useful organizations were solved. activity was restored. In particular, newly created non-profit organizations operating in socially significant areas were located in these houses on the right of gratuitous use.

The scope of state support for civil society institutions has been expanded, public funds for supporting civil society institutions have been created under local Councils of People's Deputies. The legal basis for the allocation of funds from the local budget for financial support of civil society institutions in the regions has been strengthened, social projects have been financed from these sources for the first time this year.

In addition, it should be noted that the accountability of non-governmental non-profit organizations to the justice and tax authorities has been simplified and completely transferred to electronic form. The indicator of timely and high-quality reporting of non-governmental non-profit organizations has increased by 35 percent. [7]

On March 3, 2021, in continuation of the ongoing reforms aimed at creating conveniences for non-governmental non-profit organizations and ensuring their freedom of activity, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5012 "State support for non-profit activities" - state non-profit organizations, protection of their freedom of activity, rights and legitimate interests" a decision was made on additional measures related to ensuring.

By this decision, from March 1, 2021:

- the total amount of funds and property received by non-governmental non-profit organizations from foreign sources (for information) during one calendar year has been increased from twenty times to one hundred times the basic calculation amount;
- the period for re-registration of a non-governmental non-profit organization and state registration of its symbol has been reduced from one month to fifteen days;
- the collection of state fees for the transfer (re-registration) of symbols of disabled people, veterans, luminaries, women's and children's public associations from the state register has been canceled;
- a state fee of 50 percent of the basic calculation amount has been established for state registration of regional non-governmental non-profit organizations;
- a separate subdivision of a non-governmental non-profit organization is considered a legal entity, the procedure for registering separate subdivisions has been canceled.

Also, within the framework of the tasks defined in the "Concept for the Development of Civil Society for 2021-2025", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6181 dated March 4, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan organized advanced training courses for representatives of 50 non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions at the Academy of Public Administration under the auspices of

It should be noted that although gradual reforms are being implemented in the field of creating conveniences and facilitating the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, ensuring freedom of their activities, increasing the number of state social orders allocated to non-governmental non-profit organizations. [8] organizations by state bodies and organizations at the expense of extra-budgetary funds, as well as an increase in the number of non-governmental non-profit organizations, it is desirable to improve knowledge and skills in preparing socially significant grant projects and their implementation. In addition, in order to improve the legal knowledge and literacy of representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations, communicating to them the requirements established by law, it is necessary to organize training courses and a series of seminars with the participation of representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations. state non-profit organizations.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that the measures being implemented serve to assist civil society institutions in our country, provide state support for their activities, and legally secure the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations at all stages of drafting laws. The results of the study show that despite the successes achieved, there is a need for further reforms to optimize the work of public associations and strengthen their role in the public life of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасида жамоат бирлашмалари тўғрисидаги Қонуни. <https://lex.uz/acts/111825>.
2. Юсупова, Г. (2007). Узбекистан: проблемы повышения статуса общественных организаций в политической жизни общества. Центральная Азия и Кавказ, (3 (51)), 165-171.
3. Янгибоев, Н. К. (2023). Формирование высокой правовой культуры—основа развития общества. Scholar, 1(17), 139-144.
4. Djurayeva, U. C., & Yoqubov, S. N. O. G. L. (2021). O 'zbekistonda millatlararo totuvlikni ta'minlashining konstitutsiyaviy huquqiy asoslari. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(11), 901-907.
5. Турсунов, С. Н. XX аср бошларида сурхон воҳасида суғориш тизимининг ривожланиши. Ўтмишга назар, 23.
6. Pardaev, T. (2022). Transfer of economic life in uzbekistan after world war II to a peaceful track: problems, results and mistakes.
7. Yusupovich, K. S. (2020). The Emergence Of Religious Views Is Exemplified By The Southern Regions. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2(10), 143-145.
8. Khojanazarov, A. Z. (2024). Medical reforms on strengthening the genefound of the population in uzbekistan. Golden brain, 2(12), 158-164.